

A Secure and Robust Approach for Distance-Based Mutual Positioning of Unmanned Aerial Vehicles

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Abstract—Unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV) is becoming increasingly important in modern civilian and military applications. However, its novel use cases is bottlenecked by conventional satellite and terrestrial localization technologies, and calling for complementary solutions. Multi-UAV mutual positioning can be a potential answer, but its accuracy and security are challenged by inaccurate and/or malicious measurements. This paper proposes a novel, robust, and secure approach to address these issues.

Index Terms—UAV, mutual positioning, security, robustness

I. INTRODUCTION

Over the past decade, the importance of unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV) has risen dramatically. Its deployment, especially in form of multi-UAV systems, has been rapidly growing in various civilian [1] and military [2] use scenarios. Particularly, multi-UAV systems are widely considered to play an indispensable role in future Sixth Generation (6G) [3] and Multi-Access Edge Computing (MEC) [4] systems.

For safe and accurate operation, as well as efficient task execution, precise localization of the UAVs is commonly crucial in such systems. While satellite positioning functionalities, such as Global Positioning System (GPS), are usually available in conventional UAV devices nowadays, their accuracy may be affected in some particular environments. Such environments are including but not limited to dense urban area, indoor space, tunnels, dense foliage, and deep valleys. Unfortunately, these are also typical deployment scenarios of some important UAV use cases, such as emergency rescue, aerial mobile base station, geological prospecting, and environment monitoring. Other positioning methods are therefore required, to complement or replace the satellite solution in such situation.

One possible answer is provided by the well developed terrestrial localization systems. These technologies are particularly feasible and reliable for consistent indoor deployment scenarios, generally relying on geolocation anchors fixed at known positions, such as landmark sensors [5], WiFi access points [6], or cellular base stations [7]. However, for emergency deployment or remote areas, it can be technically unfeasible or cost-prohibitive to install sensors or WiFi devices, and the mobile networks can be hardly accessible, either.

As an alternative approach, in this paper we investigate the mutual positioning, a.k.a. cross-positioning of multiple UAVs, which exploits the spatial diversity of different devices to achieve accurate localization. Like all other localization systems, multi-agent mutual positioning can be realized either direction-based or distance-based [8]. While the few

existing research on this topic are mostly assuming direction information to be available [9], [10], in this study we focus on the distance-based option due to its low implementation complexity and less sensitivity to the line-of-sight constraints.

While multi-UAV mutual positioning is following the same geometrical principle as other approaches, it is challenged by the lack of reliable landmarks. The positions of reference UAVs, unlike those of satellites or terrestrial anchors, are neither static nor accurate. Moreover, in complex radio environments, the mobility of UAV can generate strong channel fading effect, leading to high dynamics in the variance of distance measurement. These challenges are calling for a novel positioning model that considers inaccurate reference position and random power of distance error, which have not yet been studied to the best of our knowledge.

Moreover, like all other radio positioning approaches, mutual positioning is exposed to the risk of attacks, e.g. jamming or measurement falsification. This security problem has been well investigated by literature in the context of terrestrial positioning, where various approaches are proposed to defend and detect malicious data. However, tailored for sensor-based localization systems, conventional solutions generally rely on fixed landmarks [11] and/or deterministic variance across UAVs [12], [13], making them infeasible for our problem.

In this paper, we present a novel secure framework for multi-UAV mutual positioning, including a Robust Gradient Descent (RGD) algorithm that localizes the target UAV from inaccurate reference positions associated with distances measured under various variances, and a confidence-based Recursive Data Anomaly Detection (RDAD) frame that detects malicious data. The remainder of the paper is organized as follows: we start with Sec. II outlining the system and attack models, then in Sec. III we introduce conventional position estimators, and develop an advanced error model to evolve them into our RGD. Based on that, we propose in Sec. IV the RDAD scheme to detect malicious attacks and further enhance the robustness of the system. In the end, we demonstrate the effectiveness of our proposals with numerical results in Sec. V, before concluding the work with Sec. VI.

II. PROBLEM SETUP

A. System Model

We consider a set of UAVs $\mathcal{U} = \{u_0, u_1, \dots, u_I\}$, each equipped with a wireless communication module and a self-

positioning module (e.g., GPS). At any given time t , every $u_i \in \mathcal{U}$ can measure its own position (x_i, y_i) inaccurately:

$$[\tilde{x}_i(t), \tilde{y}_i(t)] = [x_i(t) + \delta_{x_i}(t), y_i(t) + \delta_{y_i}(t)], \quad (1)$$

where the error $(\delta_{x_i}, \delta_{y_i}) \sim \mathcal{N}^2(0, \sigma_{p,i}^2/2)$. This position is periodically measured, and broadcast together with the variance $\sigma_{p,i}^2$ in a beacon signal. Upon the reception of such a beacon signal from u_i , every other $u_j \in \mathcal{U}$ nearby is not only informed about the position of u_i , but also able to estimate the distance $d_{i,j}(t)$ between them therefrom:

$$\tilde{d}_{i,j} = \left(\sqrt{(x_j - x_i)^2 + (y_j - y_i)^2} + \delta_{d_{i,j}} \right)^+, \quad (2)$$

where $x^+ \triangleq \max\{0, x\}$. Depending on the specific mechanism of distance estimation, the error $\delta_{d_{i,j}} \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma_{d,i}^2)$ may originate in the random channel fading, noise, interference, or jitters; and the variance $\sigma_{d,i}^2$ may be either consistent or random, either dependent on d_i or not. Without loss of generality, in this work we assume that $\sigma_{d,i}^2$ is a random variable independent from d_i , and that it can be acquired by u_0 from the received beacon. Due to the limits in radio link coverage and speed of UAVs, the errors caused by mobility during the transmission latency of the beacon signals can be neglected. For convenience of analysis and discussion, in this study we focus on one arbitrary UAV, index it as u_0 , and assume it is able to receive the beacon signals from all other u_i where $i \in \{1, 2, \dots, I\}$. From here on, we simply notate $d_{i,0}$ as d_i . As illustrated in Fig. 1, our aim is to implement an accurate estimator $[\hat{x}_0, \hat{y}_0] = \Phi(\tilde{x}_0, \tilde{y}_0, \mathbf{b}_1, \mathbf{b}_2 \dots \mathbf{b}_I)$, where $\mathbf{b}_i = [\tilde{x}_i, \tilde{y}_i, \sigma_{p,i}^2, \tilde{d}_i, \sigma_{d,i}^2]$ is u_i 's beacon signal.

Fig. 1: Concept of the multi-agent mutual positioning

B. Attack Model

As discussed in Sec. I, $J \leq I$ UAVs out of u_1, u_2, \dots, u_I may be compromised by attacks (taking u_0 's point of view, itself is

always trustworthy). In this study we consider four different attack modes as explained below.

1) *Deterioration*: In this mode, the attacker is able to increase the variances $\sigma_{p,i}^2$ and $\sigma_{d,i}^2$ for the compromised u_i , and u_0 is aware of this deterioration in the measurements of position and distance. Thus, the beacon signal received by u_0 can be modeled as $\check{\mathbf{b}}_i = [\tilde{x}_i + n_{x,i}, \tilde{y}_i + n_{y,i}, \sigma_{p,i}^2 + \sigma_{\Delta p,i}^2, (\tilde{d}_i + n_{d,i})^+, \sigma_{d,i}^2 + \sigma_{\Delta d,i}^2]$, where $(n_{x,i}, n_{y,i}) \sim \mathcal{N}^2(0, \sigma_{\Delta p,i}^2/2)$ and $n_{d,i} \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma_{\Delta d,i}^2)$. We refer to $[\sigma_{\Delta p,i}^2, \sigma_{\Delta d,i}^2]$ as the attacking vector (AV). Such effect can be achieved by jamming the beacon signals of u_i and the GPS.

2) *Variance*: This mode is similar to the deterioration mode, except that it prevents u_0 from being aware of the introduced error. In other words, the received beacon can be modeled as $\check{\mathbf{b}}_i = [\tilde{x}_i + n_{x,i}, \tilde{y}_i + n_{y,i}, \sigma_{p,i}^2, (\tilde{d}_i + n_{d,i})^+, \sigma_{d,i}^2]$, where $(n_{x,i}, n_{y,i}) \sim \mathcal{N}^2(0, \sigma_{\Delta p,i}^2/2)$ and $n_{d,i} \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma_{\Delta d,i}^2)$. Such effect can be commonly achieved either by tampering the original \mathbf{b}_i through a man-in-the-middle attack, or by directly hijacking u_i to falsify its position information.

3) *Bias*: In this mode, the attacker is able to bias the measured position (x_i, y_i) without affecting the rest information in \mathbf{b}_i , so the beacon signal received by u_0 can be modeled as $\check{\mathbf{b}}_i = [\tilde{x}_i + \nu_{x,i}, \tilde{y}_i + \nu_{y,i}, \sigma_{p,i}^2, \tilde{d}_i, \sigma_{d,i}^2]$, where the AV $[\nu_{x,i}, \nu_{y,i}]$ remains constant over the time. Like the variance mode, it can be achieved either with a man-in-the-middle attack or by hijacking u_i .

4) *Manipulation*: This mode is an enhanced version of the bias mode. In addition to biasing the measured position, the attacker tampers the variances $\sigma_{p,i}^2$ and $\sigma_{d,i}^2$ to zero: $\check{\mathbf{b}}_i = [\tilde{x}_i + \nu_{x,i}, \tilde{y}_i + \nu_{y,i}, 0, \tilde{d}_i, 0]$.

Motivated by the fact revealed in [14], that a low penetration rate can make data-injection attacks more covert but yet effective, we allow the attacker(s) to commit attacks only at a random part of the beacon signals sent by the compromised UAV, by a penetration rate of r_{atk} . This further leads us to define two different attacking schemes when more than one UAVs are compromised, namely

1) *Uncoordinated*: where the attack is committed randomly and independently at every compromised UAV; and

2) *Coordinated*: where the attack is always committed at all compromised UAVs simultaneously.

III. ROBUST MUTUAL POSITIONING

A. Least Square and Maximum Likelihood Estimators

A straightforward and widely applied solution for multi-sensor positioning is the least square estimator (LSE):

$$[\hat{x}_0, \hat{y}_0] = \arg \min_{[x,y]} \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} \left| \sqrt{(\tilde{x}_i - x)^2 + (\tilde{y}_i - y)^2} - \tilde{d}_i \right|, \quad (3)$$

where $\mathcal{I} = \{0, 1, 2 \dots I\}$ and $\tilde{d}_0 = 0$. As a non-linear minimum mean square error (MMSE) estimator it can be efficiently solved by the gradient descent algorithm [12].

The LSE is neglecting the difference in measurement accuracy among various UAVs u_i , which degrades its precision and convergence efficiency when the measurements are significantly variant in quality. To address this issue, the maximum likelihood estimator (MLE) can be designed as

$$[\hat{x}_0, \hat{y}_0] = \arg \max_{[x, y]} \mathcal{L}(\tilde{x}_0, \tilde{y}_0, \mathbf{b}_1, \mathbf{b}_2 \dots \mathbf{b}_I | x, y). \quad (4)$$

Leveraging the Bayesian estimation it can be transformed into

$$[\hat{x}_0, \hat{y}_0] = \arg \max_{[x, y]} f_{x_0, y_0}(x, y | \tilde{x}_0, \tilde{y}_0, \mathbf{b}_1, \mathbf{b}_2 \dots \mathbf{b}_I). \quad (5)$$

Taking an approximation that $\sqrt{(\tilde{x}_i - x)^2 + (\tilde{y}_i - y)^2} - \tilde{d}_i$ is a Gaussian variable $\varepsilon_i \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma_i^2)$ for all $i \in \mathcal{I}$, (5) is further transformed into a weighted LSE (LSE):

$$[\hat{x}_0, \hat{y}_0] = \arg \min_{[x, y]} \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} \frac{\left| \sqrt{(\tilde{x}_i - x)^2 + (\tilde{y}_i - y)^2} - \tilde{d}_i \right|}{\sigma_i}. \quad (6)$$

Especially, if $\sigma_i = \sigma$ for all $i \in \mathcal{I}$, it is equivalent to the LSE defined in Eq. (3).

B. Error Conversion

Now consider the error model shown in Fig. 2. While the distance \tilde{d}_i is measured from the actual position (x_i, y_i) of the reporting u_i , the target UAV u_0 is only able to obtain its inaccurate position measurement $(\tilde{x}_i, \tilde{y}_i)$, and will consider the distance measurement as thereon based (the blue path in Fig. 2). Thus, the effective distance error $n_{d,i}^\Delta$ depends on not only $n_{d,i}$, but also an extra error $n_{d,i}^\Delta$ (the red dashed line).

Fig. 2: Error model mixing position and distance errors

The distribution of $n_{d,i}^\Delta$ is as complex as analytically intractable (detailed derivation emitted in this paper due to the length limit). Nevertheless, it can be precisely approximated by a non-zero-mean Gaussian distribution $\mathcal{N}(\mu_i^\Delta, (\sigma_i^\Delta)^2)$. Both μ_i^Δ and σ_i^Δ can be well fitted as paraboloid functions of \tilde{d}_i and $\sigma_{p,i}$: a numerical fitting based on 1000 random samples per combination $(\tilde{d}_i, \sigma_{p,i})$ is shown in Fig. 2. Furthermore, since μ_i^Δ and σ_i^Δ are independent from $\sigma_{d,i}$, we have $n_{d,i}^\Delta \sim \mathcal{N}(\mu_i^\Delta, (\sigma_{d,i}^\Delta)^2)$ where $\mu_i^\Delta = \mu_i^\Delta$ and $(\sigma_{d,i}^\Delta)^2 = \sigma_{d,i}^2 + (\sigma_i^\Delta)^2$.

Fig. 3: Paraboloid fitting of the Gaussian model for $n_{d,i}^\Delta$

C. Robust Gradient Descent Algorithm

Since the overall noise can be Gaussian approximated, the WLSE in Eq. (6) can be still adopted under position errors as

$$[\hat{x}_0, \hat{y}_0] = \arg \min_{[x, y]} \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} \frac{\left| \sqrt{(\tilde{x}_i - x)^2 + (\tilde{y}_i - y)^2} - \tilde{d}_i + \mu_i^\Delta \right|}{\underbrace{\sigma_i^\Delta}_{\varphi_i(x, y)}}. \quad (7)$$

And the gradient of the target function is

$$\begin{aligned} \nabla \left(\sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} \varphi_i \right) &= \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} \left[\frac{\partial \varphi_i}{\partial x}, \frac{\partial \varphi_i}{\partial y} \right] \\ &= [x, y] \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} \frac{-2 \text{sgn}(\varphi_i)}{\sigma_i \sqrt{(\tilde{x}_i - x)^2 + (\tilde{y}_i - y)^2}}. \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

Therewith, we can design the RGD method as outlined in Algorithm 1, where the parameter ϵ sets the convergence floor, K constrains the iteration number, α is the step length factor, γ the step length discount when over-descended, and m the momentum to stabilize the descending process. Especially, Line 6 applies the error model conversion to suppress the impact of position error, Line 10 normalizes the weight factors for different UAVs' measurement with respect to the least precise one, so as to keep the convergence speed on a reasonable level regardless of the overall measurement quality.

IV. RECURSIVE DATA ANOMALY DETECTION

The RGD algorithm can be vulnerable to attacks in two aspects: the attackers may 1) distort/falsify the position and/or distance measurements, so as to degrade the overall measurement quality; or 2) falsify the reported variance of measurements, so as to misdirect the descent from the direction of gradient, or to destabilize the algorithm. A secure solution is

Algorithm 1: Robust Gradient Descent

```

1 Specify:  $\epsilon, K, \alpha, \gamma, m$ 
2 Input:  $x_{\text{init}}, y_{\text{init}}, \mathcal{U}, \{\mathbf{b}_i : \forall u_i \in \mathcal{U}\}$ 
3 Initialize:  $\hat{x}_0 \leftarrow x_{\text{init}}, \hat{y}_0 \leftarrow y_{\text{init}}, U_0 \leftarrow +\infty$ 
4 for  $k \in \{1, 2, \dots, K\}$  do // Limit number of iterations
5   foreach  $u_i \in \mathcal{U}$  do
6     Obtain  $(\mu_i^\circ, \sigma_i^\circ)$  from  $\mathbf{b}_i$  // Error conversion
7      $D_i = \sqrt{(\hat{x}_i - \hat{x}_0)^2 + (\hat{y}_i - \hat{y}_0)^2}$ 
8      $s_i = \text{sgn}(D_i - \tilde{d}_i + \mu_i^\circ)$ 
9   end
10   $\sigma_{\text{max}} = \max_{u_i \in \mathcal{U}} \sigma_i^\circ$  // Weight normalization
11   $\Delta_x \leftarrow m\hat{x}_0 + \frac{\alpha}{\|\mathcal{U}\|_0} \sum_{u_i \in \mathcal{U}} \frac{s_i(\hat{x}_i - \hat{x}_0)\sigma_{\text{max}}}{D_i\sigma_i^\circ}$ 
12   $\Delta_y \leftarrow m\hat{y}_0 + \frac{\alpha}{\|\mathcal{U}\|_0} \sum_{u_i \in \mathcal{U}} \frac{s_i(\hat{y}_i - \hat{y}_0)\sigma_{\text{max}}}{D_i\sigma_i^\circ}$ 
13   $\hat{x}_0 \leftarrow \hat{x}_0 + \Delta_x, \hat{y}_0 \leftarrow \hat{y}_0 + \Delta_y$ 
14   $U_k \leftarrow \frac{1}{\|\mathcal{U}\|_0} \sum_{u_i \in \mathcal{U}} \frac{|D_i - \tilde{d}_i + \mu_i^\circ| \sigma_{\text{max}}}{\sigma_i^\circ}$ 
15  if  $U_k > U_{k-1}$  then // Over-descended
16     $\alpha = \alpha\gamma$  // Reduce step length
17  else if  $(U_{k-1} - U_k) / U_{k-1} \leq \epsilon$  then // Converged
18    break
19  end
20 end
21 return  $(\hat{x}_0, \hat{y}_0, U_k)$ 

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therefore in demand to *i*) protect the RGD algorithm from false data; and *ii*) identify abnormal data from normal ones.

To meet these requirements, we propose a two-stage recursive RDAD scheme as described in Alg. 2. The upper stage is basically executing the RGD algorithm, one step by each iteration, but first calling the lower-stage recursion to identify and reject suspicious data before invoking RGD. The lower stage is a confidence-based classification, given a reference position (\hat{x}_0, \hat{y}_0) of u_0 , it calculates the absolute error θ_i in distance measurement for every $u_i \in \mathcal{U}$ that $i \neq 0$, and estimates its cumulative density ξ_i w.r.t. the converted mixed error model (Lines 11–12). Particularly, the converted error scale σ_i° is forced to be lower-bounded by a predetermined value σ_{min} , in order to protect the algorithm from destabilization by extraordinarily low σ_i° (Line 10). If ξ_i exceeds a predetermined confidence degree Ξ , the measurement \mathbf{b}_i will be classified as suspicious. In each iteration of the upper stage, the reference position is always reset to the local position measurement of target UAV u_0 (Line 5), for it is the only trustworthy anchor that is guaranteed unaltered for u_0 in potential existence of attackers. Then the lower-stage executes recursively, running for up to L iterations, in each iteration invoking the one-step RGD to improve the reference position, and rejecting one most suspicious data, i.e. identifying it as anomaly.

V. NUMERICAL SIMULATIONS

To demonstrate our analyses and evaluate our proposals, numerical simulations were conducted. We considered one target UAV and nine measuring UAVs that are randomly deployed w.r.t. a uniform distribution over a $30 \text{ m} \times 30 \text{ m}$ map, and tested our solution as well as baseline methods regarding different scenarios of attacks and error models. Especially, when testing attacking scenarios, we considered

Algorithm 2: Recursive Data Anomaly Detection

```

1 Specify:  $\Xi, N, L, \sigma_{\text{min}}, \epsilon, \alpha, \gamma, m$ 
2 Input:  $\mathcal{U}, \{\mathbf{b}_i : \forall u_i \in \mathcal{U}\}$ 
3 Initialize:  $(\hat{x}_0, \hat{y}_0) \leftarrow (x_0, y_0), U_0 \leftarrow +\infty$ 
4 for  $n \in \{1, 2, \dots, N\}$  do // Upper stage recursion
5    $(\hat{x}_0, \hat{y}_0) \leftarrow (x_0, y_0)$  // Reset trustworthy local anchor
6   for  $l \in \{1, 2, \dots, L\}$  do // Lower stage recursion
7     Update  $(\hat{x}_0, \hat{y}_0)$  with Algorithm 1,  $K = 1$  // One-step RGD
8     foreach  $u_i \in \mathcal{U} \setminus \{u_0\}$  do
9       Obtain  $(\mu_i^\circ, \sigma_i^\circ)$  from  $\mathbf{b}_i$ 
10       $\sigma_i^\circ \leftarrow \max\{\sigma_i^\circ, \sigma_{\text{min}}\}$  // Counter manipulation
11       $\theta_i = \left| \sqrt{(\hat{x}_i - \hat{x}_0)^2 + (\hat{y}_i - \hat{y}_0)^2} - \tilde{d}_i + \mu_i^\circ \right|$ 
12      Compute the CDF  $\xi_i = P_{\theta_i}[\theta_i | \mu_i^\circ, (\sigma_i^\circ)^2]$ 
13    end
14     $j \leftarrow \arg \max_{u_i \in \mathcal{U}} \xi_i$ 
15    if  $\xi_j > \Xi$  then
16      Remove  $u_i$  from  $\mathcal{U}$  // Reject suspicious data
17    else
18      break
19    end
20  end
21  Update  $(\hat{x}_0, \hat{y}_0, U_k)$  with Algorithm 1,  $K = 1$  // One-step RGD
22  if  $U_k > U_{k-1}$  then // Over-descended
23     $\alpha = \alpha\gamma$  // Reduce step length
24  else if  $(U_{k-1} - U_k) / U_{k-1} \leq \epsilon$  then // Converged
25    break
26  end
27 end
28 return  $(\hat{x}_0, \hat{y}_0, \mathcal{U})$ 

```

three measuring UAVs to be jammed/hijacked at a penetration rate of 0.5. More details of the setup are listed in Tab. I.

TABLE I: Simulation Setup

	Parameter	Value	Remark
System	Map size	$30 \text{ m} \times 30 \text{ m}$	
	$I + 1$	10	# UAVs
	$\sigma_{\text{p},i}^2$	$\sim \mathcal{U}(0.1, 2.1)$	position variance / m^2
	$\sigma_{\text{d},i}^2$	$\sim \mathcal{U}(0.1, 0.9)$	distance variance / m^2
	M	1000	# Monte-Carlo tests per scenario
Attackers	J	3	# compromised UAVs
	r_{atk}	0.5	penetration rate
	$[\sigma_{\Delta\text{p},i}^2, \sigma_{\Delta\text{d},i}^2]$	$[50 \text{ m}^2, 50 \text{ m}^2]$	AV: deterioration & variance
	$[\nu_{x_i}, \nu_{y_i}]$	$[5 \text{ m}, 5 \text{ m}]$	AV: bias & manipulation
Positioning	ϵ	$1 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m}$	convergence floor
	K	15	max. iterations RGD
	$[N, L]$	$[15, 5]$	max. iterations RDAD
	α	0.9	initial step length factor
	γ	0.9	step length discount
	m	1×10^{-5}	momentum
	Ξ	99%	confidence degree
	$(\sigma_{\text{min}}^\circ)^2$	0.1 m^2	lower bound of variance

A. Robustness Assessment

We tested our RGD algorithm under different attacking scenarios, both with and without the RDAD scheme. For the purpose of benchmark, we also tested RGD in an attack-free scenario. The results are shown in Fig. 4.

In the scenario of deterioration attacks, as Fig. 4a shows, RGD and RDAD are exhibiting similar performance, since it is hardly possible for the confidence-based RDAD scheme to identify compromised UAVs from normal ones with imprecise

measurements, as they are honestly reporting the variance. Compared to the attack-free baseline, both methods converge faster when attacked, due to the significantly increased weights of normal UAVs in the RGD procedure. But they end up with a slightly higher positioning error when converged, which is inevitably caused by the worsened overall data quality. Especially, such effects are more significant when the attacks at different UAVs are uncoordinated rather than coordinated.

Against variance attacks, both RGD and RDAD methods are similarly and sufficiently robust regarding the final accuracy, while RDAD is converging faster than RGD. Moreover, variance attacks are more effective against RGD when committed uncoordinated, but more effective against RDAD coordinated.

Against bias attacks, RDAD shows a good robustness, rapidly converging to a high accuracy regardless of the coordination among compromised UAVs. RGD, on the other hand, is working similarly well as RDAD under uncoordinated bias attacks, but significantly impacted by coordinated attacks.

At last, when attacked in the manipulation mode, the accuracy of RGD is dramatically degraded, with the error more than tripled in comparison to the attack-free baseline, regardless the coordination of attacks. To the contrary, RDAD effectively protects the system from attacks of this type.

In summary, our proposed RGD algorithm is robust against deterioration, variance, and uncoordinated bias attacks, but sensitive to coordinated bias attacks, and vulnerable to manipulation attacks. Its shortages, nevertheless, can be well resolved by our RDAD scheme.

B. ROC Analysis of the RDAD Scheme

RDAD can be sensitive to the specification of confidence level Ξ , which determines its misdetection and false alarm rates in anomaly detection. As an example, the X_i -sensitivity of RDAD under coordinated bias attacks was evaluated through 10 000 Monte-Carlo tests and the result is illustrated in Fig. 5. As the confidence degree increases, the algorithm becomes more tolerant to measurements with low likelihood, so that the false alarm rate drops, with a higher misdetection rate as the price. The overall positioning accuracy is therewith also influenced, but the impact is not monotonic of Ξ .

The relation between the false alarm rate r_{FA} and the misdetection rate r_{MD} is the key feature of any detecting algorithm, commonly known as the receiver operating characteristic (ROC). The lower bound of all ROC curves is a straight line segment $r_{MD} = 1 - r_{FA}$ over $r_{FA} \in [0, 1]$, which implies a blind guess that randomly identifies data by ratio of r_{FA} as anomalies, regardless their content. The ROC curve of an arbitrary rational detector must lie below this line, and the farther it distances from this bound, the better the detector is.

The results of ROC analysis to RDAD in different attack scenarios are shown in Fig. 6. Once again, we see that our proposed approach exhibits a good performance in detecting attacks in modes of variance, bias, and manipulation. Especially, the manipulation attack, which we have in Sec. V-A demonstrated to be the most effective one on RGD, can be the most accurately identified by RDAD. In contrast, deterioration

(a) Attack mode: deterioration

(b) Attack mode: variance

(c) Attack mode: bias

(d) Attack mode: manipulation

Fig. 4: Convergence of the proposed methods under attacks

Fig. 5: Ξ -sensitivity of RDAD against coordinated bias attacks

(a) Uncoordinated attacks

(b) Coordinated attacks

Fig. 6: ROC of RDAD against attacks of different modes.

attacks, like discussed in Sec. V-A, can be hardly detected due to its nature that cannot be distinguished from endogenous measurement errors. Furthermore, declining such deteriorated measurements with increased error will not be helpful but only destructive to the positioning accuracy, as long as they are neither biased or falsified in variance. Nevertheless, some use scenarios may still require a sensitive detection to such kind of attacks. This can be straightforwardly solved by applying a hard threshold on the measurement error scale σ_i^o , which

is trivial and out of the scope of our work. In addition, the detection performance of RDAD is generally better against coordinated attacks than against uncoordinated ones, which agrees with the intuition that coordinated attacks are more exposed to the detector due to the significant pattern.

VI. CONCLUSION AND OUTLOOKS

In this paper, we have investigated the problem of multi-UAV mutual positioning, identified its use scenarios and technical challenges, and proposed a novel solution to address both the accuracy problem and the security risk. With numerical simulations, we have verified its robustness and detection accuracy against attacks of different modes.

Yet there is one issue not addressed in this work but worth to remark, that due to the limited effective range of mutual radio positioning, compromised UAVs may locally outnumber normal ones in some regions and therewith break through the defense of our methods, even if they are only a minority in the global UAV set. Assessment of this risk and development of countering measures can be interesting for follow-up studies.

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REFERENCES

- [1] H. Shakhatreh, A. H. Sawalmeh *et al.*, “Unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs): A survey on civil applications and key research challenges,” *IEEE Access*, vol. 7, pp. 48 572–48 634, 2019.
- [2] R. Shakeri, M. A. Al-Garadi *et al.*, “Design challenges of multi-UAV systems in cyber-physical applications: A comprehensive survey and future directions,” *IEEE Commun. Surv. Tutor.*, vol. 21, no. 4, pp. 3340–3385, 2019.
- [3] W. Jiang, B. Han *et al.*, “The road towards 6G: A comprehensive survey,” *IEEE Open J. Commun. Soc.*, vol. 2, pp. 334–366, 2021.
- [4] Z. Liu, Y. Cao *et al.*, “Multi-UAV network assisted intelligent edge computing: Challenges and opportunities,” *China Commun.*, vol. 19, no. 3, pp. 258–278, 2022.
- [5] P. Abouzar, D. G. Michelson *et al.*, “RSSI-based distributed self-localization for wireless sensor networks used in precision agriculture,” *IEEE Trans. Wirel. Commun.*, vol. 15, no. 10, pp. 6638–6650, 2016.
- [6] C. Yang and H.-r. Shao, “WiFi-based indoor positioning,” *IEEE Commun. Mag.*, vol. 53, no. 3, pp. 150–157, 2015.
- [7] S. Dwivedi, R. Shreevastav *et al.*, “Positioning in 5G networks,” *IEEE Commun. Mag.*, vol. 59, no. 11, pp. 38–44, 2021.
- [8] T. Kim Geok, K. Zar Aung *et al.*, “Review of indoor positioning: Radio wave technology,” *Appl. Sci.*, vol. 11, no. 1, p. 279, 2020.
- [9] T. Maki, T. Matsuda *et al.*, “Navigation method for underwater vehicles based on mutual acoustical positioning with a single seafloor station,” *IEEE J. Ocean.*, vol. 38, no. 1, pp. 167–177, 2013.
- [10] F. Wen, J. Wang *et al.*, “Auxiliary vehicle positioning based on robust DOA estimation with unknown mutual coupling,” *IEEE Internet Things J.*, vol. 7, no. 6, pp. 5521–5532, 2020.
- [11] J. Won and E. Bertino, “Robust sensor localization against known sensor position attacks,” *IEEE Trans. Mob. Comput.*, vol. 18, no. 12, pp. 2954–2967, 2019.
- [12] R. Garg, A. L. Varna *et al.*, “An efficient gradient descent approach to secure localization in resource constrained wireless sensor networks,” *IEEE Trans. Inf. Forensics Secur.*, vol. 7, no. 2, pp. 717–730, 2012.
- [13] B. Mukhopadhyay, S. Srirangarajan *et al.*, “RSS-based localization in the presence of malicious nodes in sensor networks,” *IEEE Trans. Instrum. Meas.*, vol. 70, pp. 1–16, 2021.
- [14] B. Han, D. Krummacker *et al.*, “Trust-awareness to secure swarm intelligence from data injection attack,” May 2023, to appear at IEEE ICC 2023, preprint available at arXiv:2211.08407.